

of Tl^I could be successfully titrated amperometrically within an error limit of less than $+0.8\%$. The experimental and calculated statistical data prove the utility of the proposed analytical procedure.

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Chromatography of certain Metal Ions on Ligand combined Ion-exchange Papers

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CHROMATOGRAPHY on papers treated with inorganic ion-exchangers¹⁻⁴ has proved to be important particularly for ionic species, as the separations are mainly based on the intrinsic selectivity of the ion-exchanger itself. Use of ligands in combination with the ion exchange material may prove it of further importance to increase the selectivity⁵. Bayer⁶ perhaps is the first to study the effect of water-soluble ligands on selectivity of ion-exchanger, because the ligands acquire a definite attachment with the matrix of the exchanger. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid can be proved to be a good example in this process. One useful advantage of this reagent is that it forms 1:1 complexes practically instantaneously with most cations regardless of their oxidation states. Therefore, the chromatographic studies of a number of

cations on papers treated with a ligand combined ion-exchanger are reported in this manuscript.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman No. 1 Paper strips (14×3 cm) in glass jars (20×5 cm). Chemicals and solvents were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of ion-exchange paper: Aqueous solutions (0.1 M) of zinc nitrate and sodium silicate were prepared. The paper strips were first dipped in zinc nitrate solution for 3–5 s and the excess reagent was drained off. The strips were then dipped in sodium silicate solution for 15 s, the excess reagent was drained off, and dried at room temperature. The zinc silicate impregnated paper was made to the EDTA-form by dipping in 1% EDTA solution for 10–15 s and then drying at room temperature. Similarly, the zinc silicate impregnated strips were dipped in 1.0 M NH_3 solution to convert them to NH_3 -form.

Test solution: Most of the cation solutions in chloride, nitrate and sulphate forms of 0.1 M concentration were prepared in water. The solutions of mercuric nitrate and chromium nitrate were prepared in 0.1 M HNO_3 . Pr, Ho, Gd, Dy and Nd solutions were prepared in alcohol. Bismuth chloride solution was prepared in 7.3 M HCl and ceric sulphate solution in 3.6 N H_2SO_4 .

Detection: Yellow ammonium sulphide was used to detect Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Bi^{3+} . Fe^{3+} was detected with aqueous potassium ferrocyanide solution; Mg^{2+} with ethanolic solution of quinalizarine; Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Cr^{3+} with 1% diphenylcarbazide in ethanol solution; ZrO^{2+} , Th^{4+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Ho^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Pr^{3+} with aqueous alizarin red S solution; Al^{3+} and Be^{2+} with 1% ethanolic solution of aluminon. A fresh solution of sodium cobaltinitrite was used for the detection of K^+ and Rb^+ . Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} were detected with freshly prepared aqueous sodium rhodizonate solution. 1% ethanolic solution of dimethyl glyoxime was used to detect Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} .

Procedure: Thin glass capillaries were used to spot test-solutions. The strips were conditioned for 15 min and the solvent was allowed to ascend 10 cm on paper. The strips were then dried at room temperature and the detection was made with the respective detecting reagents.

Results and Discussion

A substance may be characterised by determining R_f value R_f of 29 metal ions on EDTA-treated papers using different concentrations of ammonia as the developing solvent are summarised in Table I. A trend of R_f values reveal that most of the metal ions having higher stability constants show lower R_f values while for K^+ and Rb^+ the values are exceptionally higher⁶. This is because the higher the

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF METAL IONS ON TREATED PAPER STRIPS IN EDTA-FORM

Sl. no.	Metal ions	R_f values				
		DIW	0.1 M NH ₃	1.0 M NH ₃	2.0 M NH ₃	6.0 M NH ₃
1.	Hg ₂ ^{II}	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2.	Hg ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00
3.	Ba ^{II}	0.87	0.00	0.87	—	0.17
4.	ZrO ^{II}	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
5.	Bi ^{III}	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00
6.	Cu ^{II}	—	0.00	0.87	0.87	0.51
7.	Cd ^{II}	0.94	—	0.92	0.91	0.90
8.	Sr ^{II}	0.84	0.00	—	—	—
9.	Ni ^{II}	0.92	0.00	0.92	0.96	0.96
10.	Co ^{II}	0.95	0.94	0.96	0.93	0.97
11.	Rb ^I	0.89	0.87	0.90	0.92	0.93
12.	K ^I	0.91	0.92	—	0.91	0.94
13.	Pb ^{II}	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14.	Ag ^I	0.26	0.37	0.82	0.81	0.86

For Al^{III}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III}, Ho^{III}, Nd^{III}, Pr^{III}, Th^{IV}, La^{III}, Ce^{III} and Mg^{II} R_f values were 0.00 in all the mediums used.

stability constant less will be the movement, hence low value of R_f . The behaviour of Ag^I seems to be unpredictable. On the basis of large differences in R_f values, a number of separations were tried. The results are summarised below.

The following binary separation were achieved on treated paper strips in EDTA-form. Binary mixtures: Ag^I—Cd^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Ni^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Co^{II}, Co^{II}—Ag^I, Ni^{II}—Ag^I, Co^{II}—Hg^{II}, Fe^{III}—Co^{II}, Co^{II}—Hg^{II} in deionized water (DIW); Ni^{II}—Hg^{II}, Ni^{II}—Hg^{II} in 1.0 M NH₃; Cd^{II}—Hg^{II}, Ag^I—Hg^{II} in 2.0 M NH₃; Ag^I—Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}—Ag^I, ZrO^{II}—Ag^I, Cd^{II}—Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}—Cd^{II}, Ag^I—Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}—Ni^{II} in 6.0 M NH₃. Separation of single metal ion from a mixture of several metal ions on treated paper strips in EDTA-form was also possible: Ag^I and Ba^{II} individually from their mixture with Th^{IV}, Ce^{III}, Al^{III}, Mn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, K^I, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III}, Ho^{III}, Nd^{III}, Bi^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Hg^{II}, La^{III} using 1.0 M NH₃ as the developer; Rb^I from its mixture with H^I, Hg^{II}, ZrO^{II}, Bi^{III}, Th^{IV}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Al^{III}, Mn^{II}, M^{II}, Sr^{II}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Dy^{III}, K^I, Gd^{III}, Ho^{III}, Nd^{III}, Pr^{III} using 1.0 M NH₃ as the developer; Ag^I from its mixture with Hg^{II}, Hg^{II}, Bi^{III} using 2.0 M NH₃ as the developer; K^I from its mixture with Hg^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ba^{II}, ZrO^{II}, Bi^{III}, Th^{IV}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Al^{III}, Mn^{II}, Sr^{II}, Be^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III}, Ho^{III}, Nd^{III}, Pr^{III} using 2.0 M NH₃ as the developer; Hg^{II}, ZrO^{II}, Bi^{III}, Pb^{II}, Th^{IV}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Al^{III}, Mn^{II}, Me^{II}, Bi^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III}, Ho^{III}, Nd^{III}, individually from their mixture with Ni^{II}, Ag^I, Cd^{II}, Rb^I and K^I using 6.0 M NH₃ as the developer.

Chromatography was also performed on treated paper strips in ammonia form and using different concentrations of EDTA as the developer. The results are presented in Table 2. Binary,

TABLE 2— R_f VALUES OF METAL IONS ON TREATED PAPER STRIPS IN AMMONIA-FORM

Sl. no.	Metal ions	R_f values				
		mol dm ⁻³ of EDTA				
		0.026	0.053	0.134	0.214	0.260
1.	Hg ₂ ^{II}	0.21	0.32	0.46	0.56	0.69
2.	Hg ^{II}	0.20	0.31	—	0.64	—
3.	Ba ^{II}	0.80	0.91	0.86	0.74	0.74
4.	ZrO ^{II}	0.00	0.15	0.26	0.38	0.87
5.	Bi ^{III}	0.56	0.82	0.85	0.82	0.88
6.	Cu ^{II}	0.82	0.83	0.86	0.87	0.96
7.	Ni ^{II}	0.97	0.93	0.92	0.95	0.96
8.	Co ^{II}	0.95	0.87	0.85	0.83	0.88
9.	Al ^{III}	0.00	0.62	0.77	0.88	0.85
10.	Be ^{II}	0.09	0.29	0.42	0.60	0.68
11.	Rb ^I	0.80	0.91	0.93	0.91	0.90
12.	Fe ^{III}	0.00	0.32	0.54	0.62	0.67
13.	K ^I	0.91	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.97
14.	Ag ^I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
15.	Th ^{IV}	0.00	0.38	0.54	0.73	0.83

ternary as well as separation of one metal ion from a mixture of metal ions were also achieved. The results are summarised below. Using 1% EDTA as the developer the following separations were achieved: Hg₂^{II}—Bi^{III}—Be^{II}, Co^{II}—Ag^I; Co^{II}—Hg₂^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Ni^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Cu^{II}, Rb^I—Al^{III}, ZrO^{II}—Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}—Ag^I, Ni^{II}—Hg^{II}, Fe^{III}—Hg₂^{II}, Ag^I—Hg₂^{II}; separation of Hg₂^{II}—Ag^I—Pb^{II}, Hg₂^{II}—Ag^I—Bi^{III}, Fe^{III}—Pb^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Pb^{II}, Pb^{II}—Hg₂^{II}, Be^{II}—K^I, Bi^{III}, Rb^I, Bi^{III}—Hg₂^{II}, Be^{II}—Bi^{III}, Be^{II}—Pb^{II} were achieved using 2% EDTA of the developer; for ZrO^{II}—Th^{IV}—Pb^{II}, ZrO^{II}—Th^{IV}—Cu^{II}, Al^{III}—Be^{II} separation, 5% EDTA was used as the developer. Separations of single metal ion from a mixture of several metal ions on treated paper strips in NH₃ form were possible to the following using 1% EDTA as the developer: Ba^{II} from a mixture of Hg₂^{II}, Hg₂^{II}, ZrO^{II}, Al^{III}, Be^{II}, Fe^{III}, Pb^{II}; Be^{II}, Al^{III}, Ag^I and Th^{IV} individually from a mixture of Ba^{II}, Bi^{III}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Rb^I, K^I; Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Rb^I and K^I individually from a mixture of Hg₂^{II}, Hg₂^{II}, ZrO^{II}, Al^{III}, Be^{II}, Fe^{III}, Pb^{II}, Ag^I; Hg₂^{II} or Hg^{II} from a mixture of Ba^{II}, Bi^{III}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Rb^I, K^I.

The effect of concentration of EDTA as the developing solvent showed a definite trend (Table 3) which could be expressed in terms of variation of R_M values. R_M is an additive property which was derived by Bate-Smith and Westall on the basis of theoretical assumptions made by Martin,

$$R_M = \log \left(\frac{1}{K_f} - 1 \right)$$

R_M values as a function of $-\log C_{EDTA}$ were determined for certain metal ions, viz. Hg₂^{II}, Fe^{III}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Be^{II}, Al^{III} and Ni^{II}, and a linear relationship was observed.

TABLE 3— R_f AND R_M VALUES OF CERTAIN METAL IONS AS A FUNCTION OF EDTA CONCENTRATION

Sl. no.	Metal ions	Values	Concentration of EDTA mol dm ⁻³			
			0.053	0.134	0.214	0.260
1. Hg ₂ ⁺⁺	R_f		0.32	0.46	0.56	0.69
	R_M		0.33	0.07	-0.105	-0.35
2. Fe ⁺⁺	R_f		0.32	0.54	0.62	0.67
	R_M		0.33	-0.07	-0.21	-0.31
3. Th ^V	R_f		0.38	0.45	0.73	0.83
	R_M		0.21	-0.07	-0.43	-0.69
4. ZrO ⁺⁺	R_f		0.15	0.26	0.38	0.45
	R_M		0.75	0.45	0.21	0.09
5. Be ⁺⁺	R_f		0.29	0.42	0.60	0.68
	R_M		0.39	0.14	-0.18	-0.33
6. Al ⁺⁺⁺	R_f		0.62	0.77	0.88	0.85
	R_M		-0.21	-0.52	-0.87	-0.75
7. Ni ⁺⁺	R_f		0.93	0.92	0.95	0.96
	R_M		-1.12	-1.06	-1.28	-1.38

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